

ARCHAEOLOGICAL EXCAVATIONS AT CHAGRITEPE: SOME QUESTIONS ABOUT THE ORIGIN OF THE EARLY NEOLITHIC IN THE MIDDLE KURA BASIN**Museibli Najaf***Dr. Sci. (History), Professor
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In recent years, researches of Neolithic monuments in Azerbaijan and South Caucasus in general have become intensive. The emergence and development stages of early agricultural farms in the context of the Middle East-South Caucasus is the main goal of these studies. From this viewpoint, Chagritepe (Çağritepe) Neolithic settlement is no exception. Although the monument suffered some destruction as a result of anthropogenic interventions during the Soviet era, it was preserved at a relatively satisfactory level for research compared to other archaeological monuments in the region. In the 50s - 70s of the last century, archaeological excavations were carried out in the settlements of this culture, such as Shomutepe, Toyratepe, Gargalar tepesi, Babadervish. Although extensive scientific information has been obtained, many questions still remain unanswered. One of them, and the most important one, is the problem of the origin, organization and connection of the Neolithic farming culture with the previous period. This scientific problem remains unsolved to this day. The excavations conducted in the nearby Mesolithic and early Neolithic camp of Damjili did not bring sufficient clarity to the issue. The purpose of the excavations in Chagritepe is primarily to investigate this scientific problem. Since the excavations have not fully completed, the monument can be primarily attributed to the end of the 7th millennium - the first half of the 6th millennium BC. A group of tools made of obsidian and flint discovered here during the excavations is analogous to the stone tools of Gobustan from the Mesolithic and early Neolithic periods. These tools, which are considered archaic for Chagritepe, give us reason to make certain assumptions about the mentioned scientific problem.

Keywords: Mesolithic, Neolithic, early farming, microtools, obsidian, flint, settlement, camp.

Introduction

One of the scientific problems that Azerbaijani archaeological science has not been able to solve so far is the emergence of early farming culture, its origin, the transition from the Mesolithic/Early, Pre-Pottery Neolithic period to the Pottery Neolithic, and determining the hereditary connection between these periods. Since the 50s of the last century, the monuments of the Neolithic farming culture in Azerbaijan have been systematically studied, but only the advanced stage of this culture has been found [1, p. 126; 2]. The issue of its origin has not been resolved not only in Azerbaijan, but in the

South Caucasus as a whole. Although the excavations carried out in the last 15 years in the Neolithic monuments in the region, especially in the Hasansu settlement, allow us to say that there are certain signs of the pre-ceramic Neolithic period (3), the solid facts to make a definite opinion about this are still unknown. Comparisons of the archaeological materials of the settlements of the early farming-cattle-breeding population and the hunter-gatherer camps of the same period (Fig. 1) have led to interesting results.

Fig. 1. Location of monuments. 1 - Chagritepe, 2 - Shomutepe, 3 - Hasansu
4. Damjili, 5 - Gobustan, 6 - Osmantepe, 7 - Kultepe.

From this viewpoint, the Chagritepe settlement in Agstafa district is interesting, and choosing of this monument is not accidental. This monument belonging to the Shomutepe culture of the Neolithic period is located 323 m above sea level in the east of Khatai village

of Agstafa district. The hill with an area of about 1 hectare (110x80 m) and a height of about 3 m is surrounded by fields on all sides (Fig. 2, 1). In 2013, a sounding pit was dug in Chagritepe, and the discovered remains of material culture showed that there are certain opportunities for researching the mentioned scientific problem.

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Fig. 2. 1 - General view of the Çagritepe settlement. 2 - remains of building No. 1, 3 - remains of building No. 10, 4 - remains of building No. 13.

General information about excavations

In 2020, extensive excavation works were started in Çagritepe. For this, a 253 sq/m area was chosen on the eastern slope of the hill. In 4 excavation seasons (2020-2023), excavations were carried out to different depths in separate squares of the excavation area. More than half of the cultural layer has been excavated, and it has now been established that the settlement has two construction horizons, replacing each other. Excavation

was extended to 2 m in squares 1A and 1B toward the centre of the hill, and raw soil was discovered at a depth of 1.7 m in the completed squares 4A and 4B at the foot of the hill. No building remains were found in these last squares. Compactly cast (sometimes more than 20) obsidian flakes, apparently representing production waste, were found in three places at different levels of the excavation site.

Fig. 3. Excavation plan of Chagritepe. Construction remains of horizons I and II.

All discovered buildings have a circular, and in few cases, an oval plan (Fig. 2, 2-4; Fig. 3). They are built with a single layer of raw bricks. The remains of building No. 1 were kept at a height of 60-70 cm, and other buildings at a height of 20-30 cm. The building remains of the upper layer of the cultural layer - horizon I have been completely unearthed. The size of bricks used in construction was close to 46x15x8/9 cm; 40x18x6 cm etc., in size. However, there were exceptions as well. Thus, building No. 12, discovered at a depth of 1.6 m in square 1 A, belonging to construction horizon II, was built with bricks measuring 24x20x5

cm, 20x18x5 cm. As a rule, the bricks used in the construction of all buildings are slightly curved in shape, which is due to the circular plan of the buildings. Some farm wells of the upper layer were also built with raw bricks. Along with these, as the excavation continued, a number of buildings of the II horizon were discovered. So far, the constructions of the II horizon have not been fully discovered in all the squares. But the buildings of this horizon are denser and relatively well preserved.

The largest building remnant of the II horizon is building No. 13, found at a depth of 1.6 m, adjacent to the southern wall of square 2A. Its diameter is 4 m. Half

of the building goes into the southern side of the excavation (Fig. 2, 3).

At the junction of the squares 3A and 3B, the remains of a large, 3.8 m in diameter, building No. 10, also belonging to the II horizon, were identified. On the south side of the building there is an entrance opening 60 cm wide (Fig. 2, 4). It is interesting that the buildings of the II horizon are larger than the buildings of the upper I horizon. The complex of such round buildings, representing the remains of dwellings, located very closely, adjacent to each other, with utility pits between them, probably belonged to one large family. So far, the remains of more than 20 buildings of different sizes have been discovered in horizons I and II (Fig. 3).

In a number of places of the excavation area, in the upper layer, up to a depth of 40-50 cm, very rarely pottery fragments belonging to the Middle Ages – 8th-10th centuries can be found. However, in square 3B of the excavation site, up to a depth of 1.8 m, ceramics belonging to the Middle Ages are intensively discovered together with Neolithic findings. It seems that in the Middle Ages, a semi-dugout house was built here and a cattle-breeder family lived locally. This idea is also

confirmed by the discovery of the remains of a wooden pole used for the roof of the semi-dugout on the wall of the excavation.

Archaeological materials from the Neolithic period are tools made of different types of stone, including flint, obsidian and bone. The materials of both horizons are the same.

Stone findings

During the excavation, elongated *querns* of different sizes were found (Fig. 4, 1). They are made of porous dark gray stone, in the middle part they have a depression as a result of long-term use. In squares 1B and 2B, 3 large querns were revealed at different depths. They are all broken in the middle. On the working surface of one of them there are traces of ocher, which may indicate its use for grinding the mineral. Grinders were also discovered, one of which was found along with a quern.

Tools from river stones are mainly *grinders* of different types (Fig. 4, 2, 3). For this purpose, mostly flat oval stones were chosen, sometimes elongated stones were used. Their surface bears traces of use.

Fig. 4. Stone and bone tools. 1-4, 6 - Chagritepe; 5 - Gobustan

In rare cases, *chopper*-type tools made of river stone are also found (Fig. 4, 4). One of such tools is made of a thick, oval-shaped river stone. The working part of the tool, located on one of the edges of the stone,

is formed with chips applied on both sides. The surface of the tool is covered with a white residue. A close analogue of this tool (Fig. 4, 5) is known from the Anazaga camp in Gobustan (4, fig. 5, 6).

Fig. 5. Stone axes (1, 2); macehead (3).

In rare cases, small *axe-type* (wedge-shaped) tools made of river stones are also found (Fig. 5, 1, 2). The end of their thick upper part is flat. All surfaces from the lower half to the working part are smooth. Traces of rubbing processing have been preserved on such tools, which descend towards the working blade. Such tools were apparently used in small-scale works.

Among the interesting finds, one can note a flattened spherical stone (Fig. 5, 3), 6.5 cm in diameter, 4

cm in height, probably representing a blank for making a *macehead* without a hole drilled in the center. It has a biconical shape and is very neat and symmetrical. The top (surface) is flat and smooth. In the lower part, the levelling work has not been completed. Stone maceheads are typical for the Neolithic monuments of the region.

Fig. 6. Anthropomorphic images. 1, 6 - Chagritepe; 2 - Nebra (Germany); 3 - Shomutepe; 4 - Arukhlo; 5 - Gobustan.

One of the interesting finds is an *anthropomorphic stone figure* (Fig. 6, 1). It was found in a deep fireplace at a depth of 1.4 m in the in the northwestern corner of the square 1B, inside the ash layer. The height of the figure is 29.5 cm, the thickness - 3.5-3.8 cm, the maximum width - 9 cm. The figure is flat-oblong, made of grey river stone, purposefully chosen for its natural shape. There are blue natural stains on the stone, which makes the appearance of the stone attractive. The surface of the stone is completely smooth because it is highly evened. For this reason, the stone is crusted.

One side of the stone is flat. The other side is convex in the central part. A side of the convex part is broken. A side of one end of the stone was probably broken on purpose and the broken part was smoothed a little. In a part near the "head", a depression was formed by the chiselling-smoothing method. In general, with light works on the stone, it has been given an abstract anthropomorphic appearance.

It is interesting to note that the hearth where the mentioned anthropomorphic figure was discovered, which obviously had some kind of cult purpose and was used for religious and ritual purposes, was located in

the middle of a large oval-shaped building No. 11 of the 2nd construction horizon. In addition, a stone object with a recess was also found in the area of the building, inside of which soot deposits and traces of fire were visible, indicating its possible use as a lamp. It can be assumed that this partially uncovered structure represents the remains of a sanctuary.

We do not know the direct analogies of this anthropomorphic figure discovered in Chagritepe. Figurines of the same configuration, but smaller in size, made of bone (Fig. 6, 2), are known from the Late Paleolithic site of Nebra in Germany (5, p. 18-19). Similar anthropomorphic figures in a similar style, but made of clay, were discovered from coeval monuments of the Middle Kura basin - from settlements such as Gargalar tepesi (Fig. 6, 3), Arukhlo (Fig. 6, 4) [2, fig. 28; 6, p. 273]. Besides, among the Gobustan petroglyphs belonging to the Mesolithic and Neolithic periods [7], female profile images with a shape very close to the figure of Chagritepe are encountered (Fig. 6, 5). In general, such figures are typical for the Neolithic and Chalcolithic periods of the South Caucasus, the Near and Middle East [8; 9; 10, pp. 59-60].

An elongated pestle made of grey river stone also attracts attention (Fig. 6, 6). The entire surface of this stone, which is 19 cm long, has been carefully smoothed. One side is thicker than the other. In the thick part, one side is convex, and its opposite side is slightly concave. As a result of such smoothing and working, the overall shape of the stone is slightly "S"-shaped. The ends are slightly flattened due to use - weak forging. This stone, which is different from traditional pestles, also resembles a slightly anthropomorphic figure with its general shape.

Obsidian and flint tools

Most of the finds are obsidian and flint tools. The flint tools are few. But obsidian tools are hundreds. Besides, numerous production wastes were discovered. Tools are on blades and flakes of various sizes. Most scrapers discovered. Large blades are rarely found. Only 3 relatively large blades found in square 3A are of interest. Two of these are blades of transparent obsidian. Both sides were retouched and used as a scraper and notched tool. The third blade is semi-transparent, semi-silver in colour. Apparently, these blades were of special importance for the ancient inhabitants of the site.

Fig. 7. Obsidian tools from Chagritepe.

Among the obsidian products, the number of tools on the flakes is sufficient, and according to this indicator, Chagritepe is different from other Neolithic monuments of the region. These tools are mainly curry-comb and scraper-type. Along with these, burins, chisels, splintered piece type tools were made. At the same time, several tools were made on the same flake or blade. There are a significant number of such multi-functional tools. Boards were retouched from both sides. As a rule, if the right side of the board is notched from the dorsal surface, the left side is symmetrically notched from the ventral surface. Both the blades and the flakes from which the tools were made are smaller in size than in other sites.

Some of the cutting tools are *micro-tools* made of obsidian (Fig. 7). These are small blades and flakes on which, through fine processing, a side scraper, an end scraper, a point, a chisel, staples and other types of tools are formed. Although micro-tools are mostly single-functional, there are also multi-functional tools. Some microtools have a small protrusion called a "handle" (Fig. 7, 7, 8). One bladelet has side notches (Fig. 7, 10). A thin long blade in the form of a puncture needle is also distinguish (Fig. 7, 13).

Some of this type tools are made with a handle (Fig. 7, 7, 8). The tool with deep notches was made on a small blade (Fig. 7, 10). Since the sides of another blade were worked a lot, it got a pencil-like shape (Fig. 7, 13).

Of particular note is the discovery of a large cone-shaped *nucleus* made of dark stripy obsidian (Fig. 8, 1). This nucleus was discovered in the southwest of square 2A, at a depth of 1.5 m. The nucleus lay in situ vertically, leaning against the wall of the building and reinforced at the base along the edges with wattle and daub. It shows negative long blade scars on surface. However, such blades have not yet been found in the excavation area. The Nucleus is 18 cm high. The diameter of the striking platform is 15.5 cm. Such large nucleus were also found in other Neolithic period monuments (Shomutepe, Gargalar tepesi, Goytepe, etc.). In the settlement of Aknashen-Khatunarkh of the Neolithic and Chalcolithic periods in Armenia, several nuclei of large size were found together [11, fig. 3.2]. However, we do not know of such a find larger than this nucleus discovered in Chagritepe.

A certain part of the stone products are made of flint tools. Most of them consist of sickle elements (Fig. 8, 2, 3). Traces of bitumen, which was used as a fixing substance, were preserved on such tools. Unlike other Neolithic monuments of the region, the number of flint tools is relatively great in Chagritepe. Although various tools were made from this raw material, just like obsidian, their variety is not rich. Sickle elements were made of bladelets, and as a rule, without secondary treatment. Only the working parts of various shaped boards were serrated or sharpened on both sides. The thick sides of the blades were placed on a wooden or bone frame, and they were laid on their sides and fixed with bitumen.

Fig. 8. 1 - obsidian nucleus; 2, 3 - flint sickle elements.

Some *archaic type tools* attract attention. These are leaf-shaped point tools made of obsidian and flint (Fig. 9). Their sides and ends are retouched on both sides, and sometimes on one side. Among such tools, we would like first mention the obsidian blade found at

a depth of 1.4 m in square 1B. This blade is notched all around, making it a multi-functional tool. On the sides, a scraper was made, on the upper end it is a point, and on the lower end it is made as splintered piece (Fig. 9, 1).

Fig. 9. Obsidian (1-4) and flint (5-7) tools.

Two more pointed-type tools were found on leaf-shaped obsidian blades at a depth of 1.8-2 m in squares 1A and 1B. The upper half of one of them is notched from the sides to a sharp end. The sides of the lower half are concave, which gave the tool the appearance of an arrowhead (Fig. 9, 3). Another tool is on a thick blade. A sharp end is made by burin blow technique. The lower end was used as a chisel, and one side was used as a scraper (Fig. 9, 4).

In Chagritepe, tools on leaf-shaped blades were also made of flint. Most of them are sharp-pointed. Some of the leaf-like blades are worth mentioning. In square 1B, at a depth of 1.4 m, a tool made of light beige-greenish flint was found along with the obsidian blade mentioned above. The sides and upper end of this tool were finely retouched, and was used as a scraper

and knife. The surface of the blade is covered in places with a white patina (Fig. 9, 5). In square 3A, at a 60 cm depth, a pale red, three-surface oblong leaf blade was found (Fig. 9, 6). It was used as a knife on both sides, and it was finely serrated on both sides towards the upper end and made a sharp-pointed. Through tearing from the sides of a leaf-shaped blade of light green flint found at a depth of 1.8 m in square 2A a sharp-pointed tool was made by nibbling retouch (Fig. 9, 7).

Point type tools made of obsidian were also found in other monuments of the Shomutepe culture - in settlements such as Shomutepe, Toyratepe, Gargalar tepesi [2, p. 100-102]. In Chagritepe, such tools were made of both obsidian and flint. Close analogies of the leaf-shaped point type tools of Chagritepe can be found among the flint tools of the more ancient monuments -

Anazaga and Kenize camps of the Mesolithic and early Neolithic periods of Gobustan (9th-7th millennia BC) [12, fig. 170, 11-13; 13, fig. 179, 1-8; fig. 6], but does not repeat them completely. Based on radiocarbon analysis, the age of the Anazaga camp was identified as 9th-8th millennia BC [14, p. 81]. These findings give reason to think that the stone industry traditions of the Mesolithic period have been preserved to a certain extent in Shomutepe culture monuments, including Chagritepe.

Bone findings

Various bone tools were found from Chagritepe. The awl type tools are more than the others (Fig. 4, 6b). In the remains of building No. 1 in square 1A, 7 units were discovered. The upper part – epiphysis was broken in three of them. One of these tools is more interesting. It is a pencil-like piercing tool. The surface of this tool discovered intact is well smoothed. The upper end is slightly thinned by incision. That ending was probably attached to a wooden handle. Due to the use, the working ends of all the awls are well smoothed. Another pencil-shaped awl was found at a depth of 1.4 m in square 1B.

Discussion

In the recent fifteen years, the studies of the monuments of the early farming period in the South Caucasus, including in the territory of Azerbaijan, have become particularly intensive. One of the main goals of these studies is to determine the origin of the ceramic Neolithic culture based on farming. Although certain considerations have been put forward on the basis of numerous findings discovered as a result of archaeological excavations, this problem has not been fully resolved yet.

I. Narimanov, a well-known researcher of the monuments of this period, wrote that the advanced stage of early farming was discovered during the excavations, but he did not give any information about the existence of layers reflecting its origin. At the same time, he noted the presence of archaic stone tools in those monuments (Shomutepe, Gargalar tepesi, Babadervish, etc.). In general, I. Narimanov associates the appearance of farming and cattle breeding in the South Caucasus and, in particular, on the territory of Azerbaijan, with such factors as favourable as favorable natural, climatic and environmental conditions and proximity, interrelationships with the cultural centres of Western Asia. At the same time, he noted that the culture found in the valley of the Kura River reflects the established economy of the early agricultural tribes of the South Caucasus [1, p. 126; 2, p. 4, 9]. But the researcher did not extensively analyse the issue of the origin of this culture, as he did not have enough archaeological facts at his disposal.

In recent years, as a result of excavations, the number of finds related to this topic has increased, and scientific and methodological methods for solving it have expanded. It should be noted that in order to solve a scientific problem, it is first necessary to correctly define it. Researchers sometimes state the absence of monuments of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic period in Azerbaijan and, thus, make a methodological error in studying the problem. In fact, early, Pre-Pottery Neolithic

camps have been studied in several rock shelters in Gobustan (Kenize, Firuz, Anazaga, etc.) and Damjili rock shelter in Gazakh district [13; 15; 4]. The early Neolithic in these camps is closely related to the previous Mesolithic strata and is a direct continuation of it. For this reason, researchers of the early Neolithic monument discovered in Damjili consider it to be typical of the Mesolithic [15].

In the Gobustan and Damjili camps, the Mesolithic lifestyle based on hunting and gathering continued in the Neolithic with hardly any changes. In this regard, a number of traditions in the field of making stone tools from the Mesolithic period were also preserved in the Neolithic period as well. From this perspective, the living standard and economy of Pre-Pottery Neolithic Azerbaijan and the South Caucasus as a whole lagged far behind the Middle East during the same period.

Thus, there was a Pre-Pottery Neolithic period based on hunting and gathering in Azerbaijan, and this period was studied in Gobustan and Damjili. However, no monuments of the Neolithic period, based on agriculture and cattle-breeding, have been discovered in Azerbaijan until now. According to the Middle East periodization, this is the B stage of the Pre-Pottery Neolithic period [16, p. 31]. The main purpose of excavations carried out in Azerbaijan in recent years is to identify and study the monuments of this stage.

Although excavations at the Chagrytepe settlement have not yet been completed, a number of archaic stone products discovered to date allow us to make some assumptions about this problem. It is interesting that such finds of Chagritepe are partially close to the materials of the Gobustan monuments, located at a relatively far distance from this settlement - on the coasts of the Caspian Sea in the east of Azerbaijan. From this point of view, first of all we can mention the obsidian microtools discovered in Chagritepe. Such tools made of flint were widely used by the Mesolithic and early Neolithic inhabitants of Gobustan.

The obsidian and flint leaf-shaped tools found in Chagritepe are more interesting. Most of them are sharp-pointed type tools. Close analogues of these tools are known from the Mesolithic monuments of Gobustan. As already mentioned, a similar chopper-type tool made of river stone found in Chagritepe was found in Anazaga camp in Gobustan. Besides, the anthropomorphic figure made of river stone found in Chagritepe is stylistically reminiscent of the Mesolithic and early Neolithic female silhouettes in the Gobustan petroglyphs.

However, Chagritepe and other Shomutepe culture settlements and Gobustan monuments are located in geographically not close to each other, in completely different climatic and geomorphological conditions. In Gobustan, which consists of mountainous and rocky relief, in the Mesolithic and Neolithic periods, including in the 6th millennium BC, synchronous with Shomutepe culture, people settled in natural rock shelters and were engaged in hunting, gathering and fishing. But the people of the Shomutepe culture lived in the plains, open fields, fertile lands in the river valleys and were engaged in agriculture and cattle-breeding. They

lived in round-plan houses built of mud bricks and partly of wattle and daub. The settlements of this culture have been preserved in the form of hills until modern times. The mentioned stone tools of Gobustan were made of flint, while the tools of the Shomutepe culture were mainly made of obsidian. In the monuments of this culture, flint is very rare compared to obsidian.

The Damjili camp is also a Mesolithic and Neolithic rock-shelter type camp in the mountainous terrain, and its ancient inhabitants were engaged in hunting and gathering due to the natural-geographical conditions of the location. Here, the tools are mainly made of obsidian. In other words, the Gobustan and Damjili camps are typologically fundamentally different from the Shomutepe culture monuments located in the plain area.

I.H. Narimanov, comparing the monuments of Gobustan and Shomutepe, quite rightly wrote: "It is possible that when the culture of farmers developed on the fertile lands of Eastern Transcaucasia, hunting tribes still lived in the Gobustan zone due to natural conditions" [1, p. 126].

The same can be said regarding the Damjili site and the monuments of the Shomutepe culture. According to researchers of Damjili, Mesolithic and Neolithic periods are closely related in this camp. According to radiocarbon analysis, these periods covered from the mid-7th millennium to the second half of the 6th millennium BC. According to the researchers of the monument, the transition from the Mesolithic to the Neolithic took place in a short period of time [15, p. 3-12]. Previously, we also thought that Damjili was promising for the investigation of the origin of the Shomutepe culture [17, p. 47].

However, the excavations of the Damjili camp showed that the hunter-gatherer Neolithic era, which closely retained the Mesolithic traditions, was synchronous with the Neolithic of the Shomutepe culture that based on agriculture and cattle-breeding in the same region, but was behind it in terms of development and fundamentally differed from it. The closely related Mesolithic and Neolithic culture, which originated in Damjili, continued and ended at this monument without further development. That is, the Damjili culture was not the basis for the origin of the Shomutepe culture, and the transition from Damjili to the Shomutepe culture did not take place. The sharp differences in the tool assemblages and in the type of economy of both cultures do not suggest such a connection. Of course, it is possible that at some stage a certain group of Damjili residents joined the agricultural population of the neighbouring Shomutepe culture. All these discussions about the Damjili site can also be attributed to the Gobustan culture, covering the Mesolithic and Neolithic periods.

In connection with the discussed topic, it would be appropriate to mention the open settlement type Osmantepe settlement, which was discovered at an altitude of 2400 m above sea level in the Nakhchivan region and partially excavated. In this monument, obsidian products are Mesolithic and early Neolithic tools, including microtools. However, radiocarbon analyses

showed that life lasted here from the second quarter to the end of the 6th millennium BC (5735-5000 BC) [18].

As it can be seen, despite the existence of a settlement of a developed sedentary farmer-cattle-breeder culture like Kultepe I belonging to the same period in the nearby plain area, the tradition of tool making in Osmantepe is typical of the Mesolithic-early Neolithic, as in Gobustan and Damjili. In other words, there was a more backward way of life in Osmantepe than in Kultepe I of the same period. Only unlike Gobustan and Damjili, Osmantepe is an open-type settlement. Here, too, the archaic character of labour tools was connected with the economic fields of the inhabitants of the settlement determined by the natural-geographical conditions - hunting and gathering. That is, such a situation does not indicate that the monument belongs to an older period. So, the ceramic farming Neolithic period in the nearby Kultepe I started in the second half of the 7th millennium BC. At the same time, the attempts to relate Osmantepe with cattle-breeding in summer pastures are not justified. Firstly, during excavations, although carried out in a limited area of the monument, no animal bones were found. However, during the Neolithic period, domestic cattle-breeding existed in settlements of the region, such as Kultepe I. Due to the weak population of the area, sedentary farmers could feed the few farm animals even in the fields around their settlements. Transhumance cattle breeding in the South Caucasus arose only in the Early Bronze Age - at the end of the 4th - beginning of the 3rd millennium BC in connection with the development of an integrated agricultural-pastoral economy, the growth of demography, population and settlements, a significant increase in the number of small ruminants on the farm and the strengthening of economic ties in the interdependent and interconnected "mountain-plain" system.

Conclusion

Thus, the excavations in Chagritepe related to the Shomutepe culture allow us to put forward certain ideas for the study of the scientific problem such as the emergence of the Neolithic farming culture in the middle Kura basin and its connection with the previous historical stage. Archaic obsidian and flint tools discovered during excavations are among the important finds for solving this problem. Certain compatibility of these tools with the stone products of the Mesolithic and early Neolithic monuments, especially the camps of Gobustan, is of interest. However, the hunter-gatherer culture in such camps (Gobustan, Damjili) which is both older than Chagritepe and also synchronous with it, was not the starting source for Shomutepe culture. Studies that are preliminary in nature show that, in our opinion, it is more correct to look for the roots of the farming-cattle-breeding Neolithic culture of the South Caucasus, including the Shomutepe culture, in the lowland areas where it spread, in the lowest layers of the settlements of these cultures. At the same time, the cultural influences of the Middle East in this matter should be taken into consideration.

However, the excavations carried out in Chagritepe expand and clarify the information about the previously known facts about Shomutepe culture. The discovered remains of the building, the succession of

construction stages create favourable opportunities for the study of the history of the Neolithic period here.

Stratified cultural layers and distinguished building horizons, discovered household buildings and archaeological artifacts create favourable opportunities for studying the Neolithic of the middle river basin.

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